

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics, Conservation and the Kronecker Delta

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 14, 2023

In classical physics, one states in words the existence of conservation of momentum and energy. An example would be an elastic collision of two particles. In particular, this conservation is imposed, it does not mathematically appear unless one describes the process by say a Kronecker delta, i.e. $\delta(\text{momentum vector before, momentum vector after})$ or $\delta(\text{energy before, energy after})$. Even in such a case, the Kronecker delta is isolated and so one still has to manually ensure that energies and momenta chosen in a calculation ensure conservation.

A Kronecker delta is mathematically equivalent to the dot product of two orthonormal states in linear algebra. This implies an operator which may obtain the particular value in question, momentum vector or energy, when operating on the state. A Hermitian matrix operator is guaranteed to have real eigenvalues and orthogonal eigenvectors, which is required. Thus, mathematically, one may postulate energy and momentum states and corresponding operators because this automatically creates the Kronecker delta which describes conservation in classical processes. This approach holds both nonrelativistically and relativistically.

The question becomes: How does one specifically describe the operator and its state? For both a relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle classical action, which describes motion, one may write: $A = -Et + px$ where E, p are the relativistic free particle values in one case and $E = p \cdot p / 2m_0$ and $p = mv$ in the other. One may note that E and p are values which may be conserved in interactions. The action shows that the operators $-d/dt$ partial and d/dx partial yield E and p respectively, but one does not have an eigenstate. This may be obtained using $i d/dt$ partial $\exp(-iEt + ipx) = E \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and $-i d/dx$ partial $\exp(-iEt + ipx) = p \exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Because one uses partial derivatives, t and x are treated as independent relative to the time and space translation operators d/dt partial and d/dx partial.

As a result, we argue that by mathematically linking a Kronecker delta associated with classical conservation with linear algebra, i.e. momentum and energy states and finding a corresponding operator by examining the classical action leads to the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. One may apply this to an elastic two particle collision to see that the Kronecker delta and its associated state/operator form describe conservation of both energy and momentum. One may ask whether $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ has any physical relevance. Two-slit interference experiments using particles with rest mass shows that it does.

Conservation of Momentum and Energy in Classical Physics

Conservation of momentum and energy appear in classical physics. The problem is that one generally has to impose them on a problem. For example, if one considers elastic scattering of two particles, one has to introduce the constraint that total energy and momentum before and after are conserved. This conservation does not naturally appear. We ask whether there is some mathematical scheme which would allow for conservation to appear naturally. A second question is: How may one express classical conservation of energy and momentum mathematically? We suggest using the Kronecker delta:

$\Delta(p \text{ vector before, } p \text{ vector after})$ ((1a)) and $\Delta(E \text{ before, } E \text{ after})$ ((1b))

Linear Algebra

The Kronecker delta, as it stands in ((1a)) and ((1b)) is isolated and so does not seem to be any different from stating conservation in words. We note, however, that the Kronecker delta arises in linear algebra for orthonormal states, i.e.

$$\langle \text{state } i | \text{state } j \rangle = \Delta(i,j) \quad ((2)) \text{ if the states are orthonormal}$$

Here the LHS of ((2)) represents a vector dot product. Each state (or vector) may be thought of as an eigenvector of a Hermitian operator which is guaranteed to have real eigenvalues and orthogonal eigenvectors. The eigenvalues then may have physical meaning.

In order for ((2)) to have physical meaning, we wish to have both momentum and energy states and corresponding operators.

Classical Action

The classical action for a free particle: Lagrangian * t, in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases is:

$$A = -Et + px \text{ if } v = x/t = \text{constant} \quad ((3))$$

For the nonrelativistic case, $E = p^2/2m_0$ and $p = mv$.

We point out that A, the classical action, includes E and p, the two variables which may be conserved. One may see that:

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = -E \text{ and } \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} = p \quad ((4))$$

((4)), however, is not an eigenvalue equation, but may be converted into one using:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \text{ and } -i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((5))$$

For a momentum vector one may use $-\text{grad}$ and $A = -Et + p \cdot r$. We note that the classical action A is a Lorentz invariant.

Using the eigenfunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a free particle seems to allow one to create a Kronecker delta which may be used to describe conservation of energy and momentum. We consider a two particle elastic collision to see this is the case.

$$\text{State before} = \exp(i p_1 \cdot r) \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) \quad \text{State after} = \exp(i p_3 \cdot r) \exp(i p_4 \cdot r) \quad ((6))$$

$$\langle \text{state after} | \text{state before} \rangle = \int d\mathbf{r} \exp((-i p_{\text{total after}} + i p_{\text{total before}}) \cdot \mathbf{r})$$

= Kronecker delta (p total before vector, p total after vector) constant.

Similarly for energy, $\int dt \exp(iE_{\text{after}} t) \exp(-iE_{\text{before}} t) = \text{Kronecker}(E_{\text{before}}, E_{\text{after}})$
We note that in linear algebra, an integral such as the one used above is formally a dot product.

Thus this math formalism automatically allows for conservation of energy and momentum without one having to add it manually.

As a result, formally linking linear algebra, namely orthogonal states of a Hermitian operator, with a Kronecker delta allows to create classical conservation of momentum and energy. The energy and momentum operators and eigenfunctions are linked with the classical free particle action, written in terms of the conserved quantities, as the action is associated with classical motion.

Physical Reality

The above arguments are strictly mathematical. At first glance, there is no reason to necessarily believe $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ carries any physical significance. $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, however, describes wave-like behaviour in space and one could test this math function by performing a two-slit interference experiment for particles with rest mass. This is the identical test which was performed to verify de Broglie's wave description of a particle with rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in seeking to describe mathematically classical conservation of energy and momentum for free particles (as in two particle elastic scattering) one is led to the Kronecker delta. Mathematically, this may be associated with the inner product of states i.e. vectors. If these states are eigenvectors of a Hermitian matrix, they are guaranteed to have real eigenvalues and orthogonal eigenvectors. Real eigenvalues correspond to physical observables. The question is: What states and operators does one use?

We consider the classical action for a free particle, which describes its motion, written in terms of the conserved quantities E, p, i.e. $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}$ with $v = x/t = \text{constant}$. This holds both relativistically and nonrelativistically, with $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2}$ and $\mathbf{p} = m_0 \mathbf{v}$ nonrelativistically. One immediately sees that $-d/dt$ partial and d/dx are operators which yield E and p, but there is no eigenvalue equation. Such equations may be easily obtained using $\exp(iA)$ where A is a Lorentz invariant. Then i/dt partial and $-\text{grad}$ partial yield E and p vector.

To test such a theory on two particle scattering, one may note that $\exp(i \mathbf{p}_1 \cdot \mathbf{r}) \exp(i \mathbf{p}_2 \cdot \mathbf{r}) = \exp(i (\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2) \cdot \mathbf{r})$, so the total momentum before is $\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2$ vector before. The eigenfunctions are orthogonal so an inner product with a final eigenvector $\exp(i (\mathbf{p}_3 + \mathbf{p}_4) \cdot \mathbf{r})$ yields the Kronecker delta, i.e. is 0 if $\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2$ vector is not equal to $\mathbf{p}_3 + \mathbf{p}_4$ vector.

Linking the Kronecker delta to linear algebra and the classical action for a free particle leads to a mathematical formalism which automatically includes conservation of energy and momentum, without it having to be imposed by hand..

$\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is in the form of wave motion, so one may perform a two-slit experiment using particles with rest mass to see if it has any physical relevance. Such an experiment was done to confirm de Broglie's wave hypothesis and shows that $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ has physical relevance.